

SMAUG

D1.3 Data Management Plan

Revision V3

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Abstract

This document contains an extensive overview of the project's Data Management Plan (DMP), providing detailed insights on how the project will handle and process store its data produced and collected.

Document Revision History

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V01	04/03/2024	Initial version	Smartlex
V02	13/03/2024	Styling, Annexes, Inputs, Corrections	AUS, SSSA, INDRA, UPM, ATH
V03	22/03/2024	Final version	Smartlex

Grant Agreement Number	101121129
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Name	Smart Maritime and Underwater Guardian
Topic	HORIZON-CL3-2022-BM-01-01
Keywords	Maritime Security and Surveillance
Start Date	1 October 2023
Duration	36 months
Description	<p>The primary goal of SMAUG is to improve the underwater detection of threats in ports and their entrance routes, by means of an integrated system capable of providing data concerning threat analysis between 3 main elements: ports security infrastructure, advanced underwater detection systems and surveillance vessels. Underwater detection and location will be performed by four primary methods: i) acoustic detection, where a series of hydrophones will listen for sounds emitted by small underwater vehicles and will be processed by artificial intelligence methods, ii) rapid sonar hull scan, used to scan ships hulls and perform harbour floor scanning, iii) high-resolution sonar inspection, to inspect objects in water with poor visibility and iv) collective autonomous location, where a swarm of autonomous underwater vehicles will act cooperatively. This will provide information to Artificial Intelligence modules, which will improve the way detecting illicit and dangerous goods and/or of threats hidden below the water surface is currently done, taking into account sources such as Unmanned Surface Vehicle Systems, (USV), underwater remote operation vehicle (ROV), UAV (Aerial autonomous vehicle) and Port current information sources. The combination of these tools will allow SMAUG to prompt solutions capable of detecting possible threats to infrastructure or vessels, as well as identify vessels with concealed goods.</p>

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Nature of the Deliverable		R — Document, report
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web	X
SEN	Sensitive information with security recommendation	
EU Classified	R-UE/EU-R - EU Classified - Restricted to SMAUG project and Commission Services – Under Decision 2015/444	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc

Keywords

Data Management, GDPR, Guidelines, DPO, FAIR, Maritime Security

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the first release of **SMAUG project's Data management plan (DMP)**. It presents the consortium's plan to manage the production, collection and processing of its data and scientific publications during and after the project. It is a living document that will be updated during the project and reviewed by the consortium at a minimum following the periodic evaluations of the project.

Each project partner handling and bearing responsibility for data collected, stored, or used in **SMAUG** will ensure compliance with the strategy outlined here. It follows EU Horizon Europe guidelines for Data Management. **Section 1** introduces the **DMP**.

Section 2 presents an overview of research and personal data that will be collected, processed, and generated in the SMAUG project. This covers contact lists, data from interviews, data for legal research, reports, frameworks, communications materials, and scientific publications.

Section 3 covers the applicable standards, guidelines, and principles that the **SMAUG** project (partners and Linked Third Parties) will follow in the management of its data collection, use, sharing and preservation. In particular, it points to the main regulation that the project complies with, i.e., the **EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016)**. It also outlines the institutional policies and procedures of **SMAUG** partners and on data management and protection of personal data.

Section 4 sets out how **SMAUG** will meet the **FAIR data requirements** guiding principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable for scientific data management. The plan outlines how **SMAUG** will make data findable (internally and externally), openly accessible (provisions for open access to scientific publications and research data), interoperable (use of common, standardised fileformats), and to increase data re-use (approach for re-use of existing research data and plans to increase the re-use of data generated within **SMAUG**).

Section 5 covers the protection of personal data, which will be collected details on management are provided in line with the **GDPR**.

Section 6 covers data security measures **SMAUG** partners will take to ensure safe and secure data storage and support good security practices.

Section 7 indicates the various information communication tools that will be used in the project and their related policies for **GDPR** compliance.

Section 8 covers ethical aspects.

Section 9 deals with the allocation of resources for data management.

Section 10 addresses the responsibilities of the partners, followed by the report conclusion in **Section 11**.

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ABBREVIATIONS	
CA	Consortium agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital object identifier
EthM	Ethics Manager
GDPR	EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EASB	External Advisory and Security Board
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant agreement
IA	Innovation Action
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LIA	Legitimate Interest Assessment
LTP	Linked Third Party
n. d.	Non-dated
OA	Open Access
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PC	Project Coordinator
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Table 1. Abbreviations

Term	Explanation
Data collection	The process of gathering information or data.
Data management plan	A plan that includes information on the handling of research data during and after the end of the project, what data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology and standards will be applied, whether data will be shared or made open access and how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project) (EC 2016).
FAIR	“Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), to ensure it is soundly managed” (EC 2016). The European Commission recommends that Horizon Europe beneficiaries make their research data FAIR.
Linked Third Party	Linked third parties are entities with a legal link to SMAUG partners that carry out the implementation of some project action.
Metadata	Data that describes other data.
Open access	“The practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the reader. In the context of R&D, open access typically focuses on access to 'scientific information' or 'research results', which refers to two main categories: Peer-reviewed scientific research articles (primarily published in academic journals) and Research data” (EC n.d.)
Personal data	“Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.” (GDPR, 2016, Art. 4(1))
Research data	“Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation.” (EC n.d.)
Scientific information	“In the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' can mean (1) peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals), or (2) research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).” (EC n.d.)

Table 2. Definitions

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1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the **SMAUG** consortium's plan to manage the production, collection, and processing of research data, personal data, and scientific publications. It is a living document—it will be reviewed by project partners and updated during the project. Each project partner handling data and responsible for data collected, stored, or used in **SMAUG** ensures compliance with the strategy outlined in this document.

The **Horizon Europe Online Manual** indicates that a project's **Data Management Plan (DMP)** should specify what data the project will generate, what data will be open, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved. Open access to research data does not necessarily mean opening all research data. The underlying principle is “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. The focus is on encouraging sound data management as an essential part of research best practices.

Good data management captures high-quality data in a documented, well-organised, well-preserved way for long-term validity and accessibility. In turn, this results in efficient and excellent research. Well-managed data are easily shared and more likely to be reused and avoid unnecessary duplication. A classical research data lifecycle includes the following steps:

- o **Planning the research:** designing research, planning data management, planning consent, planning data collection, establishing processing protocols and templates, and exploring existing data sources.
- o **Collecting data:** collecting data, capturing data with metadata and acquiring existing third-party data.
- o **Processing and analysing data:** entering, digitising, transcribing and translating data; checking, validating, cleaning or anonymising data; deriving, describing, and documenting data; managing and storing data; analysing and interpreting data; producing research outputs and citing data.
- o **Publishing and sharing data:** requires establishing copyright, creating user documentation, creating discovery metadata, defining appropriate access to data, and publishing or sharing data.
- o **Preserving data:** requests migrating data to the best format and media, storing and backing up them, creating preservation documentation and preserving the data.
- o **Re-using data:** this step includes conducting secondary analysis, undertaking follow-up research, conducting research reviews, scrutinising findings, and using data for teaching and learning.

SMAUG is guided by these steps in its data management process. Smartlex s.r.l issued a questionnaire to all **SMAUG** partners to indicate details on the data they will collect, process, and produce throughout the project. This was completed in February 2024 and will be updated as the project develops. The partners have been instructed to notify Smartlex s.r.l of changes as they occur so they can be reflected in the DMP in a timely manner. Details are included in **Annex 1** of the Excel spreadsheet describing all project data, including personal data.

1.1 Methodology

Smartlex s.r.l introduced the partners to the methodology adopted and the needs of a DMP during the kick-off meeting in Valencia on 2-3 October 2023 (M1).

A further online seminar was offered on Monday, November 13, 2023 (M2), to give specific instructions and guidance to partners on the **Data Management Plan**.

In December (M3), Smartlex s.r.l created an online Excel document with instructions for collecting data for the first release of the **DMP** by M6 from each partner to identify research data in use or to be developed. For each update, Excel includes a description of the dataset that will be developed, processed, shared, etc., during **SMAUG's research activities (Annex 1)**. Where information was unavailable at the time of compilation, an indication for the expected month in which the partner is expected to produce the information and organise their management was inserted.

Analysing the shared spreadsheet, Smartlex s.r.l developed the first release of the **DMP**, including the rules to be applied for the project data management, considering the Open Research Data purposes and exceptions (i.e. IPRs and data protection issues, the need to prevent misuse of research results, and other possible commercial interests that must be balanced against the main purposes of the open access policy).

The **DMP**, conceived as a living document, will be regularly updated and released at the expected dates unless earlier releases are needed due to emerging issues to ensure data management procedures comply with the internal policies of participating universities and institutions, with national and EU legislation and with Horizon Europe guidelines. They have been and will be rigorously applied, irrespective of the country where the research is conducted.

The **European General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/6791 (GDPR)** and its national implementations are a paramount reference for data management purposes, both for internal purposes and regulatory ones. The project partners ensure that all project research activities are compliant with the **GDPR** and national data protection laws in force.

According to **Article 16 and Annex 5 (Specific Rules)** of the Grant Agreement and **Article 9 (Access Rights)** of the Consortium Agreement, the development of **SMAUG's** concept and objectives will be available in terms of open-access **research data**.

As far as research data are concerned, the open access policy will be limited only in the following circumstances:

- o **Data protection issues:** personal data is eventually collected, stored, and processed in compliance with the current EU and national legal framework (EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679, GDPR).
- o **Public safety (misuse):** the Consortium will prevent any possible misuse of research outputs by deciding not to make some of the research outputs available in open access.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2016.119.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ:L:2016:119:TOC

- **Intellectual property rights (IPR):** The Consortium will identify possible limits descending from the IP protection of its results or data and dataset used to achieve the individual purposes of the project.
- **Commercial interests:** The consortium might evaluate possible commercial exploitation of the project's results.

These four cases are considered exceptions to the CC BY NC 4.0 licence by which third parties may share (*i.e.* copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (*i.e.* remix, transform, and build upon) the material for any purpose, even commercially. Eventually a security exception will be added in due course if that exigency is flagged by the SMAUG Security Officer.

The full terms of the license can be found at: [CC BY 4.0 Legal Code | Attribution-Non Commercial 4.0 International | Creative Commons.](#)

The Open Access research data include the establishment of a **FAIR ecosystem**:

- **Findable:** the repository offers easy and user-friendly search features.
- **Accessible:** the search mask identifies access rules for each research data uploaded (e.g. authentication).
- **Interoperable:** datasets or research data will be uploaded considering the opportunity to be integrated with other datasets/research data.
- **Reusable:** a homogeneous description of data (therefore metadata) increases the opportunity to replicate and/or combine data following the open licence.

This **FAIR ecosystem** will be achieved through the following strategy:

- The Consortium opened a “Community” referred to as **SMAUG on the Zenodo repository**. This will allow the collection and storage of research data following the **OpenAIRE** standards for EU Commission-funded projects. The community is accessible here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/smaugeuproject>, and it will be managed and populated by the project partners under the supervision of the Project Coordinator.
- The dissemination and communication activities will contribute by boosting the publication and sharing of research outputs on **SMAUG's communication channels** (*i.e.* website, social channels, etc.) under the coordination of AUSTRALO and UPM partners.

As far as publications are concerned, the Consortium opted to promote the Open Access policy as long as it is feasible and convenient, considering the target and the rank of the given journal/publisher. In any case, each Partner will ensure that the selected publisher/journal allows open access to the sharing of the preprint version of publications stemming from the project's research activities.

To allow the scrutiny of the limitations to open access, particularly with respect to limits descending from the **IP protection** of results and research data and to security concerns, partners to the Consortium have established a notice procedure to be followed before any dissemination activity takes place (*e.g.*, conference papers, publications). The Security Officer, in combination with UPM, will oversee the dissemination of the results.

This **DMP** is aligned with the prescriptions of the GA, namely with (**Article 13. Confidentiality and Security; Article 14. Ethics and Values; Article 15. Data Protection, Annex 5: Specific rules**)

Eventual ethics and/or security issues arise, and they are brought to the attention respectively of the Security officer and of the ethics team of Smartlex s.r.l in charge of reviewing the management and handling of ethical issues in the course of **SMAUG's activities under T1.5**. This task drives the consortium partners in the **DMP** implementation, monitors and makes sure that the **DMP** procedures are correctly and fairly implemented and will give feedback and opinions to the Project Coordinator on any ethical issues and questions that may arise during the performance of the project's activities and their implementation.

As appropriate, the ethics and security issues will be brought to the attention of the external Ethics and Security Board.

At a consortium member level, data protection compliance for administrative activities is assessed by the **institutional Data Protection Officers** and possibly – even if at this stage excluded – participatory activities by the institutional Research Ethics Boards or Committees, as required by national legislation.

1.2 Structure of the Report

Section 2 presents an overview of research and personal data that will be collected, processed, and generated in the **SMAUG project**.

Section 3 covers the applicable standards, guidelines, and principles that the **SMAUG project** (partners) will follow in the management of its data collection, use, sharing and preservation. It also outlines **SMAUG partners' institutional policies and procedures on data management**.

Section 4 sets out how **SMAUG** will meet the FAIR requirements, as laid out by the FAIR Guiding Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable for scientific data management.

Section 5 covers the protection of personal data. For personal data that will be collected, details on management are provided. Section 6 covers data security and measures that the **SMAUG** partners take to ensure safe and secure data storage and support good security practices. **Section 7** indicates the various information communication tools that will be used in the project and their related policies for **GDPR** compliance. **Section 8** covers ethical aspects. **Section 9** deals with the allocation of resources for data management, section 10 with the responsibilities of partners, and **section 11** concludes the **DMP**.

2. Overview of SMAUG Data

The main types of data (including personal data) that will be collected, processed and/or produced during the project include:

- Academic and grey literature on relevant topics, including reports from similar/related projects
- Relevant ethics codes, guidelines, policies, and legal texts
- Notes and results of interviews, surveys, workshops with experts and stakeholders

- o Personal data and views on selected technologies of individuals taking part in public engagement activities
- o Contact lists (of relevant stakeholders and for the mailing list)
- o Signed information sheet and consent forms
- o Media articles
- o Project work plans and internal notes
- o Deliverables, articles and PowerPoint presentations
- o Dissemination materials, including the website, newsletters, videos and social media posts.

Depending on the purpose of the data and data protection concerns, data may be made public, shared only within the consortium, or kept in institutional repositories.

In December 2023, **SMAUG partners** were asked to provide details on the data that they will collect, process and/or produce as part of the project.

These details are presented in **Annex 1: Overview of SMAUG Data**. For convenience, the table below presents a list of the personal data processed in **SMAUG**.

Please see **Annex 1** for more details.

Partner	Task	Nature of personal data
INDRA	T1.3, T3.3, T7.4	Names and email addresses, questionnaires
ATH	T3.2, T5.6	Site surveys, questionnaires, interviews
AUS	T7.1, T7.2	Email, forms, questionnaires, logs, images, video
UPM	T7.3	Email, images, video,

Table 3. Overview of SMAUG personal data

3. Applicable Standards, Guidelines, and Principles

SMAUG partners adhere to their own institutional policies and procedures on data management. The table below expands on the partner policies and data management procedures for data collection, use, sharing and preservation:

Data protection standards, guidelines and principles	
1	European Parliament and the Council, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation or GDPR);

2	European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe, open science – Early knowledge and data sharing, and open collaboration, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021, https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/18252
3	European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Your guide to intellectual property management in Horizon Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/409260
4	Applicable national data protection regulations
5	Research integrity standards, especially the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

Table 4. The SMAUG project follows these standards, guidelines and principles

4. FAIR Data: Meeting the FAIR Requirements

4.1 The FAIR Guiding Principles

Based on the publication from the European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe, “Open science - Early knowledge and data sharing, and open collaboration” 2021, this section outlines how SMAUG operationalises this.

The figure below illustrates the FAIR Guiding Principles:

Figure 1. FAIR Guiding Principles

4.2 Making Data Findable, Including Provisions for Metadata for SMAUG

4.2.1 Internal Provisions

The **SMAUG internal project** documents and administrative data are stored in Microsoft Teams, which are provided and managed by INDRA. It is accessible to all the partners working on the project. The coordinator of **SMAUG** is the repository owner and can give other people access to the Project folder and editing rights. INDRA's IT staff also have administrative access rights. The **SMAUG** project manager monitors folders and file names to ensure the data repository is consistent together with all partners. To make data findable and reusable, the following measures are in place:

- o **Location:** All documents are stored in relevant folders. There are currently 13 master folders: Contracts, Deliverables, Meetings & Minutes, Proposal, Resources, WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, and WP7. Each of these folders has sub-folders where related documents can be stored in various formats, e.g., Word documents, PDFs, Excel spreadsheets, PowerPoints or other standard data formats. Each **SMAUG** partner is responsible for storing documents related to their work in the project in the correct location.
- o **Naming of files: Filenames** must adhere to the following convention:

Minutes of Meetings: SMAUG.Minutes – TTTxx - ddmmyyyy – Vzz where:

- o TTT is the type of meeting:
 - o KOM: Kick-off meeting
 - o FSM: Follow-up Short meeting
 - o COP: Council of Partners meeting
 - o PST: Project Steering Team meeting
 - o SAB: Ethics and Security Advisory Board meeting
 - o xx is the meeting number starting with 01
 - o ddmmyyyy: day, month and year of the meeting
 - o zz is the version of the document starting with 01
 - o This ensures any partner requiring access to the information can easily find it.
- o **Reports and documents:** All **SMAUG** reports and documents contain information on authors and contributors, clear version numbering, dates, how to cite, and keywords. The details of this protocol are provided in the **SMAUG T1.3 Quality Management Plan**.

INDRA is responsible for curating the internal project data after the end of the project (30 September 2026) and when the **SMAUG TEAM repository** will be taken down.

4.2.2 External Provisions

The following provisions will ensure that **SMAUG outputs** are findable externally:

- All public deliverables (in some cases redacted versions) and outputs are published on the **SMAUG website** and indexed on OpenAire via Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/smaugeuproject>).
- Zenodo issues a **digital object identifier (DOI)** to each **SMAUG** upload to ensure effective and persistent citation.
- Search keywords are provided for every deliverable and report.
- All partners have been advised of data availability, changes to data and their location to facilitate access and wider sharing (as deemed fit).
- Guidance on “how to cite” is included for easier citation of **SMAUG deliverables** and outputs or in the Quality Management Plan.

4.3 Making Data Openly Accessible

4.3.1 Open Access to Scientific Publications

Per clause 16.3 of the **SMAUG Grant Agreement and Annex 5** (Specific Rules), each **SMAUG** beneficiary will ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) via green or gold open access routes to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. A minimum of 10 peer-reviewed scientific publications are planned. **SMAUG** has a dedicated budget for this purpose. Per the GA, beneficiaries must:

- Deposit, as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; the beneficiary also aims to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
- ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication.
- The bibliographic metadata is in a standard format and includes all of the following: **(1)** the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”; **(2)** the name of the action, acronym and grant number; **(3)** the publication date, **(4)** length of embargo period if applicable, and **(5)** a persistent identifier.

In addition to open-access publication in academic journals, partners intend to present **SMAUG** work on the following platforms:

- Website of SMAUG (<https://smaug-horizon.eu/>) and of participating partners.
- Open Research Europe (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu>), which is an open-access publishing platform for EU-funded projects.
- Zenodo public repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/smaugeuproject>)

4.4 Open Access to Research Data

In line with **SMAUG GA clause 16.3**, the project provides open access to research data unless an exception applies. For example, if making specific parts of the research data openly accessible would jeopardise the achievement of the project’s main objective, it is not in line with data protection requirements or constitutes a trade secret.

Before sharing any data, either with the consortium or externally, we will ensure that no disclosive information is included. Data may be disclosive where if, despite the removal of obvious identifiers, characteristics of a dataset in isolation or in conjunction with other datasets might lead to the identification of the individual, business or other entity to whom a record belongs.

Public deliverables and outputs (redacted, if needed) are published on the [SMAUG website](#) and on [Zenodo](#). Deliverables will be uploaded one month after submission, ensuring that SMAUG public deliverables are available as soon as possible. Until approval from the EC, deliverables will be watermarked with the note **“Pending approval by the European Commission”**.

The table below identifies the key characteristics of this repository.

Zenodo	
Scope	All research outputs from across all fields of research can be included.
Relevant institutional partner	Anyone can use it. INDRA will create an SMAUG account and deposit SMAUG data.
Pros	Uploads get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make them easily and uniquely citeable. Create and curate your community for a workshop, project, department, or journal, into which you can accept or reject uploads. Funding — can identify grants, integrated in reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via OpenAIRE. Generalist repository. Easy, instant tracking of views and downloads. Flexible licensing — as not everything is under Creative Commons
Size limits	It accepts up to 50GB per dataset (you can have multiple datasets), and there is no size limit for communities.
What can be uploaded	Publications (book, book section, conference paper, journal article, patent, preprint, report, thesis, technical note, working paper, etc.), posters, presentations, datasets, press releases, newsletters, promotion material, images (figures, plots, drawings, diagrams, photos), software, videos/audio and interactive materials such as lessons.
Retention period	Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.

Table 5. Zenodo repository

4.5 Making Data Interoperable

SMAUG partners exchange information using a variety of means as appropriate, e.g., e-mail and Microsoft Teams.

To allow data exchange and reuse between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc., **SMAUG** ensures data interoperability by consistently using common, standardised file formats (see **Annex 1: Overview of data used in this project**). The consortium uses file formats that, even when originating in or primarily used with proprietary software and/or code, are accessible with open-source software. When available and not otherwise in conflict with data security, protection or processing measures and requirements, the consortium uses open-source software applications. Through its use of common, standardised file formats and software, **SMAUG** seeks to facilitate any legitimate and lawful data re-combinations with different datasets from different origins.

4.6 Increase Data Re-use (through clarifying licences)

This section outlines **SMAUG's approach** to re-using existing research data and plans to increase the reuse of data generated within the project.

4.6.1. Re-use of existing data

Some of **SMAUG's work** will, where appropriate and needed, re-use (aggregate, synthesise or analyse) materials (e.g., figures, tables, quotations) from existing literature (academic, policy or other documents). In such cases, they will be referenced appropriately and acknowledged, and any necessary permissions for re-use will be obtained. **SMAUG partners** will use literature (both academic and press articles) relevant to the tasks.

4.6.2. Increasing re-use of SMAUG Results

The deliverables classified as public will be made publicly accessible via the project website and [Zenodo repository](#).

SMAUG deliverables use a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. According to this, a user can share (i.e., copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) or adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially) under the following terms:

- The user must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. A user may do so in any reasonable manner but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses the user or their use.
- The user may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

In line with the **SMAUG Consortium Agreement (Section 8.1)**, the results of work performed within Work Packages in the Project are owned by the party(ies) that generate(s) them. Joint ownership is governed by **GA Annex V: Specific Rules, “Ownership of results”** and unless otherwise agreed (see the CA Section 8.2):

- o each joint owner shall be entitled to use their jointly owned results for non-commercial research activities on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s), and
- o each joint owner shall be entitled to otherwise exploit the jointly owned results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license) if the other joint owners are given (a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice and (b) fair and reasonable compensation.

5. Protection of Personal Data

5.1 Purposes and Legal Basis of Personal Data Processing

The project will collect and process personal data only if it is necessary for its research and engagement activities, i.e., research, consultations, interviews, and events, and to share its findings and results with stakeholders via mailings, the website, and newsletters. Our primary legal basis for processing personal data is an individual’s consent. Individuals have the right to withdraw consent at any time without any negative consequences. The project will also use “legitimate interest” as a legal basis for the processing of personal data, as specified further in section 5.5 below on the Management of the stakeholder network and mailing list for the newsletter. See **Annex 2** on the Legitimate Interest Analysis. In summary, personal data is collected from members of the consortium, members of external organisations or individuals in their capacities as experts, respondents, or participants with their consent or on the basis of legitimate interest.

Annex 1 identifies SMAUG activities that will collect personal data and indicates the purposes of the collection, the types of data that will be processed, its storage formats, modes of collection, sharing, location, accountability, and access arrangements. **SMAUG** mostly collects personal data that is largely available in the public domain. The list of personal data processed in **SMAUG** has also been summarised in **Table 3: Overview of SMAUG personal data**.

5.2 Data Minimisation, Storage, and Retention

SMAUG minimises the amount of data collected and processed and the length of time it retains the data. In line with **GDPR requirements**, partners commit to collecting personal data in a way that is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they were processed. **SMAUG partners** ensure that personal data about an individual is sufficient for the purpose it holds it for in relation to that individual, and partners will not hold any more information than what is properly needed to fulfil that purpose.

SMAUG stores personal data securely on password-protected computers. Personal data is only used for the specific purpose for which it is collected (e.g., workshop management or travel arrangements)

and will be deleted immediately after that purpose is fulfilled unless legally required to be retained (noting here that the **SMAUG Grant Agreement** requires project data to be archived correctly at least five years after the balance payment is paid, and that some organisations may have longer saving policies for audit/legal reasons). Publications related to activities involving human participants do not contain any personal data or reference to personal data unless the participants expressly wished to be acknowledged and/or consented to this.

SMAUG complies with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679). For activities for which informed consent is eventually required, partners will provide research participants with a clear description of **SMAUG activities** and clear information on the procedures used for data control and anonymisation.

5.3 Rights of Individuals

Individuals have the following rights:

- Right to request from the **SMAUG's partner's data controllers** access to the personal data **SMAUG** has that pertains to them.
- Right to request the data controllers to rectify any personal data errors to ensure accuracy.
- Right to request the data controllers to erase their personal data.
- Right to request the data controllers to restrict their personal data's future processing or object to its processing.
- Right to data portability - upon request, the data controller will provide a data subject with a copy of the data **SMAUG** has regarding them in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format.
- As the processing of personal data occurs based on consent, individuals have the right to withdraw their consent at any time, and **SMAUG** will cease further processing activities involving their personal data. However, this will not affect the lawfulness of any processing already performed before consent has been withdrawn.
- Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority, such as their national data protection authority.

If partners plan to re-use personal data, they will ask participants for their consent for this re-use and be given the opportunity to withdraw their data. During the project, **SMAUG** offers participants the option to withdraw themselves and their data in line with the policy communicated to them before the specific activity. As part of each communication the participant receives, **SMAUG** allows them to opt out of further communications and have their data deleted from the project's records.

If the project uses secondary personal data, it only does so from public sources or sources authorised for such use (either specifically for our research and engagement activities or generally for any secondary use).

All consortium partners will adopt good data security procedures. This helps avoid unforeseen data usage or disclosure, including the mosaic effect (i.e., obtaining identification by merging multiple

sources). Measures to protect data include access controls via secure logins, installation of up-to-date security software on devices, and regular data backups.

Section 6 of this document further covers data security aspects.

Where obtained, recorded information (audio and/or visual) is given special consideration to ensure that privacy and personal identities are protected. Participants who are photographed or filmed during SMAUG activities are provided with a consent form to read and sign. The signed forms are kept on file with the lead partner of the specific activity in their institutional repository.

An internal Media Release Form was issued to all project partners for permission to use photos and/or videos of **SMAUG consortium** partners throughout the duration of the project (see **Annex 4** of the present deliverable). INDRA is responsible for keeping track of all meeting participants who have signed the form. Partners who sign this form can nevertheless request that particular photos or videos be removed by contacting the **SMAUG communication team** (info@smaug-horizon.eu).

5.4 International Data Transfers

In cases of personal data transfers to and from non-EU countries, **SMAUG partners** will comply with the **GDPR requirements**. We ensure that personal data is only transferred outside of the EU in compliance with the conditions for transfer set out in **Chapter V of the GDPR**, as interpreted by the Court of Justice of the **European Union**², the **European Data Protection Board**³, and relevant national Data Protection Authorities. In case personal data are transferred from a non-EU country to the EU, such transfers will comply with the laws of these non-EU countries. Non-EU countries include countries of the SMAUG partners, namely the UK and Serbia.

5.5 Management of Stakeholder Network and Mailing Lists

SMAUG has three different contact lists: The Stakeholder Network list, the project internal mailing lists and the mailing list for its newsletter.

The stakeholder contacts are developed as part of the WP7- D7.1 Task on - **Stakeholder Collaboration Framework** led by AUSTRALO, and the plans are described in detail in the Impact Master Plan (D7.1). AUSTRALO manages these documents with eventual contributions from all partners. They are securely stored on **Microsoft Teams**.

5.5.1. Mailing List for the Newsletter:

This mailing list was developed for communication and dissemination purposes as part of WP7 in order to share relevant information about the project with potentially interested parties. It is managed and has access (only emails) by AUSTRALO, and contact details are kept on the sending platform (Brevo).

The legal basis for building this contact list is as follows:

² Case C-311/18 *Facebook Ireland and Schrems*. <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/liste.jsf?td=ALL&language=en&jur=C.T.F&parties=schrems>

³ https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/edpb/files/consultation/edpb_recommendations_202001_supplementarymeasurestransferstools_en.pdf; https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/recommendation-standard-application-approval-controller-binding_en

- Consent: people requesting to receive the **SMAUG newsletter**.
- Legitimate interest: Partners will provide contact details of experts from their networks who might be interested in hearing news about the project and working in related areas and topics. The newsletter will include the possibility of opting out.
- Smartlex s.r.l developed a **Legitimate Interest Assessment (LIA)** in October 2023 to provide a justification for the processing of personal data in the **SMAUG project** as part of communication and dissemination activities. The LIA is included in **Annex 2**.

5.5.2. Project's Internal Mailing Lists:

These mailing lists were created for internal communication among the project partners and are hosted on the same server as the project website. In October (M1), INDRA created an online Excel document in the project teams' repository for partners to input their emails in the relevant Work Package. In December (M3), following partners' input and consent, the mailing lists were created, along with the website, using the format **WPx@smaug-horizon.eu** (where x corresponds to the work package number). Only individual members on the list have permission to send and receive emails to and from the included members for security reasons. The server is situated in an ISO-certified data centre (ISO 27001 and 22301), ensuring confidentiality, integrity, and data availability. ONLY the project coordinator (INDRA) has the authority to manage email additions and removals from the lists.

5.6 Special Category of Personal Data

Although not included in the **SMAUG personal data processing**, for the sake of completeness and awareness, we explain here that a particular category of personal data is defined as “personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.” (**GDPR, Art. 9**)

No particular categories of data are foreseen to be collected or solicited from participants. Moreover, eventually, in any stakeholder activities, we will collect data with participants’ explicit consent, and participants will be free to decline to provide such data.

These data will be processed by INDRA, Athanor Engineering, and AUSTRALO and anonymised/pseudonymised locally. Only anonymised/ pseudonymised data will be transferred to the project consortium for processing to meet its research objectives, following the transfer arrangements laid out in the present **DMP**. The sharing of this particular category of personal data will be limited to what is strictly necessary, as identified by the guidance provided in **T3.5**, which will follow the principle of data minimisation. Access to these data will be restricted only to partners involved in T1.3, 3.2, 3.3, 5.6, 7.1, and 7.2, 7.3,7.4 as captured in **Table 3: Overview of SMAUG personal data**.

Only anonymised data will be shared in aggregate form in public reports and publications.

5.7 DPO or Privacy Policies

Where applicable, partners have appointed a **Data Protection Officer (DPO)**, and the relevant contact details of the **DPO** will be made available to all data subjects involved in the research activity. For partners not required to appoint a **DPO** under the **GDPR**, a detailed data protection policy for the project is kept on file in the project Microsoft Teams. The table below indicates which partners have a **DPO** and those who have developed a data protection policy.

PARTNER	DPO or data protection policy?	DPO CONTACT INFO or link to data protection policy?
INDRA + INDRA Sistemas	DPO	macanora@indra.es
Athamor Engineering	DP Policy	https://athanor-engineering.com/en/solutions-for-maritime-security-en/
AUSTRALO	DPO	jose@australo.org
CIVIPOL	DPO	protection-donnees@civipol.fr
Drammen Port	DPO	https://drammenhavn.no/en/about-english/
Elefsina Port	DPO	dpo@olesa.gr
Elistair	DPO	t.penet@elistair.com
Fav Innovation	DP Policy	www.favit.es
French Ministry of Interior	DPO	fabrice.mattatia@interieur.gouv.fr
FV	DPO	data@fundacion.valenciaport.com
Hellenic Coast Guard	DPO	https://www.hcg.gr/en/contact/
Heraklion Port	DPO	tsantilasoffice@gmail.com
ITML	DPO	vchatzi@itml.gr
Lemvos	DPO	daniel.severinsen@lemvos.com
Smartlex s.r.l	DP policy	www.smartlex.eu
Spanish Customs	DPO	dpd@correo.aeat.es
SSSA	DPO	dpo@santannapisa.it
University of Piraeus Research Center	DPO	boile@unipi.gr
UPM	DPO	proteccion.datos@upm.es
USN	DP Policy	personvernombud@usn.no
VETE	DPO	timmu@veteengineering.com
Vicomtech	DPO	dpd@vicomtech.org / rgpd@vicomtech.org

Table 6. Partners with DPOs or Data Protection Policies

5.8 Data Controllers

The **project's data controllers** (for personal data) will make the necessary notifications and/or obtain the required authorisations for collecting and processing data. The **SMAUG data controllers** for each activity are the task leads (either sole or joint controllerships). The table below identifies the activities for which each partner is a data controller.

Partners	Activities for which they are <u>personal</u> data controllers
INDRA	T1.1, T1.3, T7.4
Athantor Engineering	T3.2, T5.6
AUSTRALO	T7.1, T7.2
UPM	T7.3

Table 7. Data Controllership

6. Data Security

During the project, **SMAUG partners** store project data in the **Microsoft Teams repository** hosted by INDRA. The Microsoft Teams repository is password protected, and only current project members with passwords can access it. **Microsoft Teams is ISO 27001-certified.**

In addition to the Microsoft Teams repository, partners may store local copies of research data on their institutional servers and/or business cloud-based servers with access controls, encryption, or password protection. Partners follow their institutional security safeguards.

All partners, as a minimum:

- o Ensure that **SMAUG research data** stored with them on their institutional servers is regularly backed up.
- o Ensure devices and data are safely and securely stored, and access controls are defined (e.g., via encryption, password protection, and restriction of the number of persons with access) at the userlevel.
- o support good security practices by protecting their own devices, installing and updating anti-malware software and anti-virus software, and enabling firewalls.
- o (In case personal data is processed), ensure appropriate security and confidentiality of the personal data, including preventing unauthorised access to or use of personal data and the equipment used for the processing (**GDPR**).
- o where necessary, the controller or processor of personal data evaluates the risks inherent in the processing and implements measures to mitigate those risks (e.g., encryption) and ensures an appropriate level of security, including confidentiality, taking into account

state-of-the-art and the costs of implementation in relation to the risks and the nature of the personal data to be protected (GDPR).

After SMAUG ends, the owners and/or managers of the repositories where the SMAUG datasets are stored are responsible for their data security.

During SMAUG and to ensure appropriate levels of security, a SMAUG INFORMATION DISSEMINATION SECURITY PLAN (Annex 5) identifying the dissemination levels and storage authorisations has been developed and will be monitored by the SMAUG Security Officer.

7. Information Communication Technology Tools and GDPR Compliance

SMAUG partners will use various information communication technology tools to conduct project activities. This section identifies these tools, describes how they are used, and explains how they comply with GDPR requirements.

PLATFORM/ TOOL	Link to policy of GDPR Compliance	How the tool is used in SMAUG
LinkedIn	https://privacy.linkedin.com/gdpr	SMAUG uses LinkedIn to post news about the project and related topics related to the project to an audience that consists of institutions, organisations, EU projects, and individuals who work/are involved in related fields.
Twitter	https://gdpr.twitter.com/en.html	SMAUG uses Twitter to share and post news about the project and its topics. It follows institutions, organisations, EU projects, and individuals who work in or are involved in related fields.
Project website	https://smaug-horizon.eu/	It is the primary source for all information during the project and after the project's end date. It is used as a main outreach tool. It is hosted on the server used by partner AUSTRALO and managed by its service provider, A2hosting . The server is located in an ISO-certified datacentre (ISO 27001 and 22301 - providing for confidentiality, integrity and data availability).
WordPress	https://en-gb.wordpress.org/about/privacy/	WordPress is a content management platform (CMP) used to manage and update website content throughout the project lifecycle.
Microsoft Teams	https://privacy.microsoft.com/en-gb/privacystatement	SMAUG project currently uses TEAMS (hosted by INDRA) for online meetings, workshops, and events. Each participant joins the meeting using their name and email address. Personal data will not be reused in any way. No information is

		stored locally (unless required for audit), and no copies are made.
Youtube	https://policies.google.com/privacy	SMAUG shares videos about the project and its topics on YouTube. It follows institutions, organisations, EU projects, and individuals who work in or are involved in related fields.
Brevo	https://www.brevo.com/legal/privacypolicy/	Brevo is a newsletter platform used to send newsletters via email to its subscribers throughout the project lifecycle.

Table 8. ICT tools and GDPR compliance

8. Responsibilities and Allocation of Resources

SMAUG has specific tasks and deliverables dedicated to data management led by Smartlex s.r.l and supported by contributions from all partners. Smartlex s.r.l is responsible for planning and overall coordination of the data management task. Each project partner who handles and is responsible for data collected, stored, or used ensures compliance with the strategy outlined in this document. Smartlex s.r.l oversees compliance with the data management plan along with INDRA as project coordinator. **Each SMAUG partner** is responsible for adhering to the strategy and procedures outlined in this document and other relevant documents.

Smartlex s.r.l will review and revise this plan, consult with partners, and implement any corrective actions as required. The DMP will be revised when new information becomes available; existing datasets become re-classified into a different data-sharing category due to emerging/newly discovered data privacy or commercial concerns, changes to data protection law, and the removal of/changes to project partners. **SMAUG partners** will notify Smartlex s.r.l when any such cases arise and advise of any updates to their institutional data management policies and procedures that might have an impact on **SMAUG’s data management**.

This deliverable will be updated during the project, and revised versions will be produced in time for the interim and final reviews.

The **Impact Master Plan D7.1 (Exploitation chapter)** covers **SMAUG's sustainability actions** for its outputs and research data.

The costs for making data **FAIR** in this project will be addressed in the next **DMP** release on M18. The following versions of the **DMP** will address how these are covered. This will eventually include information on the resources for long-term preservation of data (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long).

9. Ethical Aspects

SMAUG partners comply with Article 14 of the GA, which states that all activities must be carried out in compliance with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international, and national laws on ethical principles. In addition, the ethical rules specified in **Annex 5: Specific Rules, “Ethics”** of the GA must also be followed.

Partners conduct research in accordance with fundamental principles of research integrity, such as those described by **ALLEA in its European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity**.⁴ These principles are reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability (ALLEA 2017, p. 4). Furthermore, the partners will avoid misconduct, namely, fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism.

In keeping with the highest standards of research integrity and to ensure the privacy, safety, and dignity of data subjects, **SMAUG partners**, with support from Smartlex s.r.l, will provide participants with project information sheets and consent forms in a language that is terms entirely understandable to the participants. These forms describe the aims, method, and implications of the research, the nature of the participation, and any benefits or risks (e.g., privacy) that might be involved. They explicitly affirm that participation is voluntary and that participants have the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw their participation or data at any time without any consequences. The forms outline how partners collect and protect data during the project (e.g., use of anonymisation) and then destroy it or reuse it (with consent). They indicate the procedures to be implemented in the event of unexpected findings. Researchers will ensure that potential participants fully understand the information and do not feel pressured or forced to give consent.

10. Other Issues

In the project's lifetime, should other ethics or data management plan issues arise, they will be addressed in the next release of the **DMP** or earlier if appropriate.

11. Conclusion

This deliverable presents the **SMAUG consortium’s plan** for managing the production, collection, and processing of its research data and scientific publications.

This deliverable will be updated and reviewed by the consortium during the project and in the final year of the project, and an updated version will be generated in advance of the final review meeting. Updates will be made to consider new data, changes in consortium policies, and changes in consortium composition and external factors (e.g., new consortium members joining or old members leaving).

Each project partner handling and responsible for data collected, stored or used in **SMAUG** ensures compliance with the strategy outlined in this document.

⁴ <http://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf>

D1.3

ANNEX 1 Data Overview

Annex 1 is an Excel spreadsheet with data formats, origins, expected sizes, utility, data users, and access levels per partner and task.

This Excel is to be uploaded with this Deliverable in the Project Portal.

Annex 1 Data
overview .xlsx

ANNEX 2: Legitimate Interest Assessment (LIA) of the creation of contact lists for stakeholder engagement and dissemination of information

October 2023

This document, prepared by Smartlex s.r.l., provides the justification for processing personal data for the **SMAUG project**, specifically for compiling a contact list of stakeholders whom we will contact periodically by means of an e-mail, press release, newsletter, or other means.

The V contact list contains the names, titles, organisations, and e-mail addresses of stakeholders whom we believe might be interested in our project's results, as well as stakeholders who have asked to be added to our contact list.

Data processing in the SMAUG project includes collecting contact details as well as sending information to contacts. Most lawful bases require that processing is 'necessary' for a specific purpose. In the instance of our project, the collection of contact data and sending contacts information about our project results are necessary for the project to achieve impact, to ensure that our target stakeholders are informed of the results of our project and how those results can help them in their efforts to incorporate ethics and societal values in the development of new and emerging technologies. Hence, our project results have a larger social purpose than simply benefiting the consortium partners ("the beneficiaries" in the EC's terminology).

Two legal documents are particularly relevant for EU-funded projects.

The first is the **Grant Agreement (GA), Article 17(1)**, which states that beneficiaries of Horizon Europe projects have an obligation to promote the project and its results: "The beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) strategically and effectively." Article 17 indicates that consortia are obliged to disseminate their results to multiple audiences, which implies the need to compile a contact list targeted at various audiences in a strategic and effective manner, i.e., not just a random list of people who visit the project's website and ask to be put on the contact list. It has to be a targeted and strategic contact list. Hence, we consider that the GA serves as a valuable justification for the **SMAUG consortium** to process personal data for this purpose.

The second is the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Article 6**, which provides several possible legal bases for the processing of personal data. For example, **Article 6(1)(a)** allows the processing of personal data with the consent of the individual (the data subject). The GDPR sets a high standard for consent to be considered valid and can always be withdrawn.

Another basis is **Article 6(1)(f)**, which allows processing necessary for the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party. Our project has a legitimate interest in processing personal data, which stems from **GA Article 17**, as referenced above. We are obliged to inform stakeholders, including the public, about our project and disseminate and communicate its results.

Legitimate interest is the most flexible lawful basis for processing but must be carefully assessed in each specific case. The existence of a legitimate interest also depends on the reasonable expectations of the persons concerned, where we use people's data in ways they would reasonably expect and, where such use would have a minimal privacy impact, and where there is a compelling justification for the processing. Most stakeholders on our contact list have their e-mail addresses on their organisation's website; that is, they have already made their contact details public. Hence, they must have a reasonable expectation that others will contact them. Others have asked to be on the contact list.

In addition, a balancing exercise must be conducted between the legitimate interests of the project and the interests of the data subjects concerned. For this balancing, **SMAUG** went by the following method to conduct the balancing exercise.

In principle, there are three elements to the legitimate interest basis. We moved to:

- identify a legitimate interest – As stated above, we have a legitimate interest, under **Article 17**, to process personal contact details, as mentioned above, in order to create an impact for our EU-funded project.
- show that the processing is necessary to achieve it. ' Necessary means that the processing must be a targeted and proportionate way of achieving our purpose. We must collect the contact details of potential stakeholders across the EU to inform them about how our project results could help them in their work developing new and emerging technologies for societal wellbeing. The processing is necessary as we could not reasonably achieve the same result in another way.
- balance it against the individual's interests, rights and freedoms – see below, where we have done a balancing test and are confident that the consortium's legitimate interests do not infringe upon the individual's interests or fundamental rights.

As noted below, our processing of personal data will not harm our stakeholders any more than any other email. We are not using people's data in ways they would find intrusive or which could harm them. We will always offer stakeholders an option to unsubscribe from our contact list.

Safeguards

Even though we believe there are no significant risks to the data subjects of their being on our contact list and sending them relevant news, we have considered safeguards to reduce further any risks, as follows: the SMAUG consortium commits to keep its contact list in a secure, password-protected file to which only a limited number of individuals will have access on a need-to-know basis.

As we wish to rely on legitimate interests as the basis for processing data on our contact list, we have conducted this legitimate interest assessment (LIA) before we start the processing. According to relevant literature and current practice, a LIA is a type of light-touch risk assessment based on the specific context and circumstances. It helps ensure that processing is lawful. Recording our LIA also

helps to demonstrate compliance in line with our accountability obligations under **GDPR Articles 5(2) and 24**.

Current practice, illustrated also by the pragmatic instructions provided, is that DPA uses checklists for the LIA. We have adapted to project needs the guidelines offered by the ICO (<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/lawful-basis/a-guide-to-lawful-basis/lawful-basis-for-processing/legitimate-interests/>). Leveraging these guidelines, the following questions have been dealt with as part of our LIA exercise. Opposite each question in the left-hand column, we give our response in the right-hand column.

First, identify the legitimate interest(s):

Why do you want to process the data – what are you trying to achieve?	We wish to inform stakeholders about the SMAUG project's development of an ethics-by-design framework to incorporate ethics and societal values in .the design and development of 3-4 new and emerging technologies.
Who benefits from the processing? In what way?	The consortium partners benefit from the processing because they can inform our contacts about the project's results. Stakeholders also benefit because they will have a set of new ethics frameworks and relevant items to support their work in research and technology development.
Are there any wider public benefits to the processing?	Yes, enhanced stakeholder capabilities from the use of the SMAUG results will render the public safer in case of future events.
How important are those benefits?	It is essential, especially if they can help researchers prioritise research ethics and integrity in the design and development of new technologies. The project will give Stakeholders the tools they don't currently have. The project consortium already includes research bodies, academics, science communication organisations, and technical experts, and they can evidence the potential benefits to other potential users.
What would the impact be if you couldn't go ahead?	It would affect our ability to fulfil our contractual obligation.
Would your use of the data be unethical or unlawful in any way?	No, we will follow good data protection practices and follow established ethical guidelines and legal safeguards.

Second, apply the necessity test:

Does this processing actually help to further that interest?	Yes, this processing will help our legitimate interest in informing Stakeholders about the development of the project’s outcomes aimed at helping them.
Is it a reasonable way to go about it?	Yes, it is the only way to contact the Stakeholders directly— apart from telephoning them directly, which would be more intrusive than an e-mail.
Is there another less intrusive way to achieve the same result?	No, see above. Calling would be more intrusive.

Third, apply the balancing test:

By applying the balancing test (based on the questions below), we consider the impact of our processing and whether it overrides the interest we have identified.

What is the nature of your relationship with the individual?	The individuals, in this case, are the Stakeholders across the EU. Stakeholders are our targets for the ethics-by-design framework being developed in our project, so this relationship is potentially significant.
Is any of the data particularly sensitive or private?	No. We are collecting only basic contact data that is already publicly available. In addition to the contact details we have compiled, some stakeholders visiting the SMAUG website have asked to be added to our contact list. We keep a log of such requests.
Would people expect you to use their data in this way?	Yes, especially Stakeholders who have put their contact details on their websites (public). Hence, they must expect that people will contact them. In addition, the circulation of e-mails informing stakeholders about EU-funded project outcomes is a widespread practice in the field, and we assume that the carefully selected stakeholders will receive this communication positively.
Are you happy to explain it to them?	Yes. We will inform our contacts about our project's mission and how its results could interest them. We will notify them about the project’s privacy policy, which will respond to the GDPR Art. 14 requirement to provide information to the data subjects.

Are some people likely to object or find it intrusive?	No, as mentioned above, they are interested in knowing about the project's results.
What is the possible impact on the individual?	There is no negative impact on the individual. We expect only a positive impact, in the sense that Stakeholders will become aware of how our project's results could help them. Typically, we would expect to e-mail our Stakeholder contacts no more than a few times a year.
How big an impact might it have on them?	As above.
Are you processing children's data?	No. We do not aim to do this.
Are any of the individuals vulnerable in any other way?	Not that we are aware of.
Can you adopt any safeguards to minimise the impact?	We want to maximise the (positive) impact of and for the project. However, as noted above, we are implementing safeguards to protect our contact list – notably, our contact list file is securely stored and password-protected, and only a few individuals can access the file. For further details, see the project's privacy policy.
Can you offer an opt-out?	Yes, we include an "unsubscribe" option for all our communications with stakeholders, such as newsletters, press releases and project flyers.

The decision on legitimate interest

Based on the foregoing, we conclude that legitimate interest, **Article 6 (1)(f)**, is an appropriate basis for our processing of personal data, as described above. We are confident that any risks to the data subject do not override our legitimate interests.

Next steps

We will inform our contacts that we are relying on legitimate interest for the processing of their contact details, and we will explain what this interest is – especially to draw to the attention of Stakeholders

how the **SMAUG codes, guidelines, and frameworks** will help to improve the design and development of new and emerging technologies with high socioeconomic impact.

We understand that if we want to process the personal data for a new purpose, we may be able to continue processing under the legitimate interest provision as long as our new purpose is compatible with our original purpose. If necessary or useful, we will conduct a new LIA to demonstrate compliance with the legislation.

We will keep this record of our legitimate interest assessment (LIA) on file in order to demonstrate compliance with legislation if required. We will keep our LIA under review and repeat it if circumstances change.

References

Article 6 and Recitals (47), (48) and (49) of the GDPR

Article 29 Working Party Opinion 06/2014 on the notion of legitimate interests of the data controller under Article 7 of Directive 95/46/EC

Article 17 of the Grant Agreement

ANNEX 3: Dissemination Plan

Below is outlined the SMAUG's dissemination Plan as described in the D7.1 Impact Master Plan:

Figure 2. Dissemination Plan Phases

➤ **Phase I: Analysis (M01-M09).** During this initial phase, the Consortium will analyse the project's framework, paying particular attention to internal and external barriers that may impede dissemination activities. Additionally, they will define priorities and actions for the project's first year. The Communication & Dissemination Leader will oversee engagement efforts to align dissemination activities with stakeholder needs, fostering general awareness about the project's objectives and anticipated outcomes. This phase will involve the preparation and delivery of branding and an initial set of promotional materials as outlined in the **SMAUG communication plan**.

➤ **Phase II: Increase impact (M09-M18).** The primary objective of Phase II is to amplify the impact and awareness established in Phase I, highlighting **SMAUG's** achievements. The Communication & Dissemination Leader will tailor the channels and strategies identified during the proposal phase (and refined in Phase I) to meet the specific requirements of Phase II. Efforts will be directed towards effectively engaging and collaborating with target groups to enhance the potential impact of the project's outcomes. Participation in workshops, tailored event organisation, and potentially hosting tutorials/webinars will enhance the dissemination process. Specific PR materials will also be developed.

➤ **Phase III: Adoption (M18-M36).** This phase will capitalise on the awareness generated in Phases I and II, attracting more potential users and customers of **SMAUG** project results. The Communication & Dissemination Leader, in collaboration with the Exploitation Leader, will assess the outcomes of Phases I and II and refine priorities, channels, and strategies as necessary. This will be

done in coordination with agile stakeholder management activities. Furthermore, activities that could sustain impact beyond the project's duration, such as continued event participation, workshops and conference involvement, and contributions to targeted online and print media publications, will be defined.

In terms of communication and dissemination, **SMAUG** aims to share project results across various phases with the appropriate audiences at the right junctures to showcase how research and innovation contribute to a **European 'Innovation Union'**. Communication initiatives will highlight the scientific excellence and competitive contributions of our multidisciplinary European consortium. The plan is tailored to the diverse nature of consortium members, enabling targeted outreach to different segments of stakeholders. Selected channels will **ensure broad visibility** and project enhancement through impactful marketing tools, including **social networks, events, external media, publications, conferences, and email marketing.**

ANNEX 4: Internal Media Release Form

The online form can be accessed here: <https://tally.so/r/npKrzZ>.

SMAUG

SMAUG EU Project- Informed Consent for Multimedia Use

Welcome!

As part of the SMAUG EU project activities, photos, videos and audio recordings may be captured during conferences and other project related events for promotional and dissemination-related purposes in print materials and on the Internet (social media and official website)

By filling in this form, you agree to having your image and/or video and/or voice recorded and published for project's related activities. You can retract your consent at any time by sending an email with Title: Unsubscribe at info@smaug-horizon.eu

Your name *

Your last name *

Organisation *

Position *

E-mail *

Social Media Profile *

Do you agree to the terms outlined above? *

ANNEX 5: SMAUG Information Dissemination Security Plan

Annex 5
SMAUG_Information [